

TIME DIFFERENCE RAYTRACE METHOD FOR RANGING AND SOUND CHANNEL PROBING

By F. H. Maltz

Naval Underwater Systems Center
New London, CT 06320

SUMMARY

A method for time delay ranging in the deep sound channel is outlined here. The method is based on modeling sound channel SSP by an N-layer model. The parameters of the model are reference sound speed C_0 , layer thickness Δz and sound speed gradient vector \mathbf{g} . For ranging purposes, it is only necessary to determine the composite parameter $(\Delta C/\Delta R)$. As shown, this can be done by differential ray trace or by using two distinct bearing angles. Another alternative is to use an analytical profile and to differentiate axial range with respect to the vertical arrival angle ϕ . The same methodology is proposed to solve the inverse problem, namely the gradient set is obtained from N independent observations of the phase gradient parameter $(\Delta C/\Delta R)$. The explicit transformation of SSP to phase gradient for an axial configuration of sources and receivers for the layered model is outlined. A simple transposition method is discussed to obtain an off-axis configuration of source/receiver allocations. All the results presented here have been restricted to ray trajectories having a single upper and single lower raphath loop. This propagation mode is generally associated with first convergence zone ranges, that is to say ranges of the order of 50 km.

INTRODUCTION

Acoustic raypath determination is important in remote sensing of sound emitters in the ocean. Examples include localization of schools of fish, ships and other sound sources. Also, both active and passive acoustic positioning and navigation system performance at long ranges is a function of sound path. In the deep ocean, sound propagates out to the longer ranges by surface ducting and via the deep sound channel. Surface ducting conditions are highly variable both geographically and temporally. On the other hand, sound channel characteristics are fairly stable ^{1,2,3}

This paper deals with time delay ranging and sound channel probing using an array of receivers. A method is discussed here which draws upon some basic ray acoustics ideas applied to otherwise conventional time delay ranging systems. The approach is based on characterizing the ray acoustics in terms of two parameters, phase velocity and its horizontal range gradient. Phase velocity is fundamental to a stratified medium since by Snell's Law, it is constant over depth and simply related to sound velocity associated with a single ray. It can be measured locally at any point on the ray trajectory. Phase velocity horizontal gradient is a characteristic of two closely spaced rays. Both phase velocity and gradient are functions of range between source and receiver. Together, they can be used to express

range implicitly as a function of time difference of arrivals (TDOA) namely, first and second order time delay measurements. If the sound speed profile (SSP) is known, then this function can be inverted to give the desired range between source and receiver. Otherwise, more than one set of time delay measurements is required to jointly estimate range and phase velocity gradient.

The inverse problem of remote sensing and estimation of the sound channel SSP when range is determined by some other means is also treated here. The same basic method is proposed for solving the inverse problem. That is, the ocean is modeled by a finite number of plane layers, each having a constant thickness and fixed sound speed gradient. Time delay measurements are made using a known source and array of receivers and these measurements related to the layer gradients as will be shown.

TIME DELAY RANGING IN THE SOUND CHANNEL

When travel time is not a function of direction but a function of range only, range can be expressed directly in terms of phase velocity and gradient. For example, consider a point source and a three point receiver array at the same depth and separated by a range R as shown in Fig (1) below

Fig. 1.

For this co-planar source/receiver, co-linear array configuration, range R can be expressed as follows:

$$\left(\frac{1}{R}\right) = \left(\frac{1}{R_0}\right) + \left(\frac{1}{\Delta R}\right) \cdot \left(\frac{\Delta C}{C}\right) \cdot c \cot^2 \theta \quad (1)$$

where

$$R_0 = \frac{(x \sin \theta)^2}{c \cdot \Delta \tau}$$

As indicated, the quantity X is the spacing between each adjacent pair of the three horizontally in-line receivers, θ is the angle between source/receiver line of sight and receiver line. The angle θ can be measured from the time delays $\tau_1 = T_2 - T_1$ and $\tau_2 = T_3 - T_2$ as follows:

$$\theta = \cos^{-1} \left(c \cdot \left(\frac{\tau_1 + \tau_2}{2X} \right) \right) \quad (2)$$

The quantity $\Delta\tau$ is the second order time delay measurement $\Delta\tau = \tau_2 - \tau_1$. The parameter c is the phase velocity and Δc is the incremental change of c corresponding to a range increment ΔR . Thus $\Delta c / \Delta R$ is the gradient parameter and eq (1) expresses an identity which holds for all $R \gg X$ and assumes only that sound propagates the same in all directions, that is, the medium is horizontally isotropic. In a horizontally isotropic medium, the phase velocity c is related by Snell's Law to the sound speed $C(z)$ at depth z as follows:

$$c = C(z) \cdot \text{sec } \phi(z) \quad (3)$$

where $\phi(z)$ is the ray angle with respect to the horizontal. Thus, phase velocity can be observed at the receiver by observing the angle ϕ thru vertical TDOA measurement τ_3 . The gradient on the other hand is related to the SSP and raypath as shown in Fig 2 below:

FIG. 2.

Fig 2. shows source A and two receiving array locations r_1 and r_2 on the sound channel axis (SCA). The receiver locations r_1 and r_2 are associated with positive and negative launch angles $\pm \phi$ respectively. For a single upper loop, single lower loop and combined loop the gradients are $\Delta c / \Delta R_1$, $\Delta c / \Delta R_2$, and $\Delta c / (\Delta R_1 + \Delta R_2)$ respectively. If the SSP as defined by the function $C(z)$ is known, the equation (1) can be inverted to give a range solution from the time delay measurement vector $\underline{T} = (T_1, T_2, T_3)$. When the SSP is not known, then two distinct time delay sets \underline{T}_1 and \underline{T}_2 are required for a single range solution. This solution also yields the phase gradient.

RAYPATH ANALYSIS

As shown above, the phase gradient can be obtained by differential raytracing in which ray-apex velocity change Δc corresponding to horizontal range increment ΔR is determined. As the two adjacent rays approach one another the phase gradient becomes $c' = \Delta c / \Delta R$ and can be obtained by differentiation using equation (3) above when the analytical form of the function $R = R(\phi)$ is known. That is to say

$$c' = c_0 / \left(dR / d \text{sec } \phi_0 \right) \quad (4)$$

where c_0 and ϕ_0 are local sound speed and crossing angle respectively at the reference depth z_0 .

Two well known SSP's are the exponential and linear profiles⁴ are as follows:

$$\left. \begin{aligned} C(z) &= c_0 e^{Az} \\ C(z) &= c_0 (1 + Az) \end{aligned} \right\} \quad (5)$$

and

with associated axial range functions

$$\left. \begin{aligned} R &= \frac{2\phi - \pi}{A} \\ R &= \frac{2 \tan \phi}{A} \end{aligned} \right\} \quad (6)$$

respectively. Differentiating these functions and using eq (4) above yields the phase gradient as follows:

$$\left. \begin{aligned} c' &= \frac{c_0 A}{2} \text{sec } \phi_0 \tan \phi_0 \\ c' &= \frac{c_0 A}{2} \csc \phi_0 \end{aligned} \right\} \quad (7)$$

respectively. The SSP can be constructed from these basic profiles by combining them in a

linear plus exponential profile⁵ or by forming a piecewise linear profile corresponding to a layered ocean model. In this latter case, the phase gradient for an N-Layer ocean model becomes

$$c' = \left(z \sum_{i=1}^N (\Delta r_i / \Delta c) \right)^{-1} \quad (8)$$

where

$$\left(\Delta r_i / \Delta c \right) = \begin{cases} \frac{\csc \phi_i - \csc \phi_{i+1}}{g_i} & \text{for } i \leq N-1 \\ \frac{\csc \phi_i}{g_N} & \text{for } i = N \end{cases}$$

In the above, $2 \Delta r_i$ is the horizontal range increment associated with the i th layer. The reference depth z_0 is taken to be SCA depth with source and receiver located on the SCA. These results can be applied to other source/receiver depths by transposition of raypath segments. Some examples are shown in Fig. 3 below:

FIG. 3

In fig. 3(a), source and receiver are at SCA depth. In figure 3(b), source and receiver are above SCA depth. For this case $\phi_s = \phi_r = 0$ and source and receiver are at the upper ray apex depth. In figures 3(c) and 3(d), source and receiver are at some intermediate depth between SCA depth and upper ray apex depth with $\phi_s = \phi_r \leq \phi$. All the above ray trajectories have the same SCA crossing angle ϕ . This is the maximum ray angle since it corresponds to the depth of minimum sound speed. Changing will give another set of ray trajectories.

REMOTE ESTIMATION OF THE SOUND CHANNEL

From the foregoing, one has the propagation model equation for the phase gradient associated with an N-layer ocean model in the form of eq(8). Equation (8) gives the phase gradient in terms of the layer gradients g_i and layer crossing angles ϕ_i . The layer crossing angles are also functions of the layer gradient g_i as seen from Snell's Law

$$c c \phi_i = (1 - (c_i/c)^2)^{-\frac{1}{2}} \quad (9)$$

where

$$c_i = c_{i-1} + g_i \cdot \Delta z$$

Thus combining eq (8) and (9) above gives the phase gradient as an explicit function of the gradient vector $\underline{g} = (g_1, \dots, g_N)$ for a given ocean model as specified by layer thickness Δz and reference sound speed c_0 . The parameter set \underline{g} can be estimated from time delay measurements using for example the three point receiving array configuration described above in which case the phase gradient observations are given from equation (1) as follows:

$$c' = (R^{-1} - R_0^{-1}) \cdot c \cdot \tan^2 \theta \quad (10)$$

where

$$R_0 = \frac{(x \sin \theta)^2}{c \cdot \Delta z}$$

and

$$\theta = \cos^{-1} \left(\frac{c(\tau_1 + \tau_2)}{2x} \right)$$

This scheme assumes that there is some additional means for estimating ϕ_0 as for example by solving for ϕ_0 the following:

$$\phi_0 = \cos^{-1} \left(\frac{c \tau_3}{y} \right) \quad (11)$$

where

$$c = c(z_0) \sec \phi_0$$

with τ_3 the TDOA associated with a vertical receiver pair separated by a distance y .

A solution for the gradient vector \underline{g} can be obtained from N distinct observations of the phase gradient using for example a bearing angle set $\underline{\rho} = (\rho_1, \dots, \rho_N)$.

Data may be obtained over fewer bearing angles by deploying multiple sources, and or exploiting multiple ray paths.

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